

Energy as Frequency, Relative Velocity and Lorentz Transformations

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In quantum mechanics, energy is associated with frequency for both a particle with rest mass and a photon. In the case of the photon, we try to show that this result follows from special relativity (Lorentz transformation) which in the photon case gives rise to relative velocities.

We consider a photon moving along the x axis and bouncing back and forth between two mirrors separated by L and moving to the right with speed v. We argue that Lorentz transformations for photons create the notion of relative velocity because $E=|p|c$, but there still exists a moving frame with velocity v. As a result, a relationship between the energies of the photon moving to the right and then to the left exists with each energy being multiplied by a respective time = 1/ relative speed. This suggests photon energy representing a frequency.

. We also note that relative velocities from the Lorentz transformations are the opposite of those associated with the times the photon spends moving from one mirror to the other.. In other words, the photon moving to the right is associated with $1/c-v$, but its time with $1/c+v$ because it looks as if the photon is moving more slowly when trying to hit a mirror that is moving away from it.

Photon and Two Velocities

The Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ has two solutions for a photon. First:

$$A=0 \text{ implies that } E = |\mathbf{p}| r/t = |\mathbf{p}| c \quad ((1))$$

Secondly, $A \neq 0$ suggests:

$$A \neq 0 = -t |\mathbf{p}| (-E/|\mathbf{p}| + \text{unit vector} \cdot \mathbf{r}/t) \quad ((2))$$

Here, the unit vector is in the direction of \mathbf{p} vector (momentum) and \mathbf{r}/t is the velocity of a moving mirror or medium interface (for refraction). One immediately sees the notion of relative velocity appearing i.e.

$$-c + \cos(\theta) v \quad ((3)) \text{ where } \theta \text{ is the angle between } \mathbf{p} \text{ and } \mathbf{r}/t.$$

The notion of relative velocity also appears from examining the Lorentz transformation as will be shown. The point we wish to make is that for: distance = speed * time, 1/ speed is proportional to time and 1/time=frequency. In other words, if one obtains a relationship:

$$E_1 / \text{relative speed 1} = E_2 / \text{relative speed 2} \quad ((4))$$

then ((4)) suggests that E_1 is like a frequency with the value of relative speed. We consider a scenario which produces ((4)), namely that of a photon bouncing between two mirrors, separated by a distance L, with both moving to the right with speed v.

Photon Bouncing Back and Forth Between Two Moving Mirrors

We use Lorentz transformations to describe a photon bouncing between two mirrors separated by a distance L . The two mirrors move with speed v to the right. We wish to show how the Lorentz transformation produces relative velocities because $E/|p| = c$. We deal with motion in one dimension, i.e. the x .

Consider a photon with E, p moving to the right. Then, as seen by the mirror on the right, it has E', p' given by:

$$\begin{aligned} |p'| &= |g - vg| |p| \quad ((5)) \quad g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \\ |E'| &= |vg - g| |E| \end{aligned}$$

Thus: $p' = gp - vgE$ ((6)) The photon reflects so it has $-p'$. In the lab frame this is $-|p''|$ because it is also seen moving to the left in the lab. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} |-p'| &= |g - vg| |-p''| \quad ((6)) \quad \text{Here } p' \text{ and } p'' \text{ are both positive. } P'' \text{ is the magnitude} \\ |E'| &= |vg - g| |E''| \quad \text{of momentum of the reflected photon seen in the lab.} \end{aligned}$$

$$((6)) \text{ and } ((5)) \text{ yield: } p'(c-v) = p''(c+v)$$

$$\text{Note: } p' = E'/c \text{ and } p'' = E''/c \text{ so: } E'(c-v) = E''(c+v) \quad ((7))$$

One may notice that $(c-v)$ and $(c+v)$ are relative velocities as seen in the lab frame. Furthermore, using distance = relative speed * time, they represent frequencies. Thus:

$$E' / (c+v) = E'' / (c-v) \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is an equation of the form: energy * time (') = energy * time (") (in the lab)

This, we argue, suggests that energy should be a frequency. This follows from special relativity and not quantum mechanics. In quantum mechanics, energy is considered to be a \hbar times a frequency, but we suggest that the origins of this result are present in special relativity. (Note, we have not used Maxwell's electromagnetic equations to find a physical frequency for the electric and magnetic fields.)

A Second Frequency in the Problem

We note that a second frequency exists in the problem, associated with the time the photon spends before striking a mirror.

For the photon moving to the right: time from the left mirror to the right = $L / (c-v)$ ((9b))

For the photon moving to the left time from the right mirror to the left = $L / (c+v)$ ((9a))

One may note that these times are the exact opposite of those in ((8)) arising from special relativity. The reciprocal of these times represents a frequency which is also a physical frequency in the problem, but not the frequency associated with energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the notion of photon energy as a frequency emerges from special relativity. We note that $E = |p|c$ and that a Lorentz transformation carries g terms, where $g = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$. Transforming E to $|p|c$ and noting that a p lab (one dimensional problem) may be multiplied by v due to the Lorentz transformation, one sees how relative velocities emerge.

We apply these ideas to a photon bouncing back and forth between mirrors separated by a length L and moving to the right with speed v . We show that: $E' 1/(c+v) = E'' 1/(c-v)$. $1/(c+v)$ and $1/(c-v)$ are proportional to time (for constant speed) and so E' and E'' should be frequencies. This idea is independent of Maxwell's equations and shows, we argue, why energy is a frequency in quantum mechanics.

We also note that there exists a second frequency in the problem, namely that associated with the time a photon spends moving from one mirror to another. In this case, the factors above are switched as the photon moving to the right is associated with $1/(c-v)$ and to the left with $1/(c+v)$.